

A STATISTICAL MODEL FOR CRACK GROWTH IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Biao Wang, Jin Dai and Shanyi Du

Research Center for Composite Materials, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, China

SUMMARY: In this paper, the crack propagation problem in composite with random microstructures was considered in detail. Along the crack path, the material is assumed to contain randomly distributed crack-arresting points which have stochastic fracture strength. The model can be used to describe a large variety of composite materials, such as continuous fiber composites and short-fiber composites, etc. The aim of this study is to calculate the probability of fracture for a given material, crack length and external load. As an example, the unidirectional fiber reinforced composite was considered in detail. The fiber strength was assumed to be a random variable with the Weibull distribution, and both the strong and weak interface between the fiber and matrix were considered. It was found the fracture strength was sensitive to the interface behavior.

KEYWORDS: heterogeneous materials, micro-mechanics, statistical model, crack growth

INTRODUCTION

The fracture toughness of heterogeneous materials, such as composites is quite different from the fracture toughness of their constituents. For example, composite materials can be obtained with much higher fracture toughness than the matrix materials. It is a well-known fact that such enhancements of fracture strength are due to the matrix, the reinforcement and the interface interaction with each other. Whereas, it is an extreme difficult task to predict the overall toughness and the probability of fracture from data on the microstructure.

Many theories have been proposed to understand the fracture mechanism of heterogeneous solids, such as fiber-reinforced composite [6,7]. The most significant works are those on fiber reinforced ceramic and the other brittle matrix composites, for example Ref.[1-5]. When the tensile load which is much lower than the utmost load of the material is applied on fiber-reinforced brittle matrix composite, closely spaced matrix cracks are induced perpendicular with the direction of the tensile load, and each crack almost completely traverses the material, but the applied load continues to be supported by unbroken fibers that bridge each matrix crack between its faces. In this paper, different fracture mechanism was considered. Along the crack path, the material is assumed to contain randomly distributed crack-arresting points which have stochastic fracture strength. For the crack to propagate over a distance Δx , it must cut off all the obstacles, such as fibers, in this area. The model can be used to describe a large variety of composite materials, such as continuous fiber composites and short-fiber composites, etc. Through the microstructural analysis, the hyperbolic differential equation was derived for determining the probability density function of crack length for given external load, the average fracture toughness of the material was also obtained. As an example, the unidirectional fiber reinforced composite was considered in detail. The fiber strength was

assumed to be a random variable following the Weibull distribution, and both the strong and weak interface between the fiber and matrix were considered. It is found that the fracture strength is sensitive to the interface behavior.

THE STATISTICAL MODEL FOR CRACK GROWTH IN COMPOSITES

Consider a general heterogeneous materials containing a straight crack as shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1: Heterogeneous material containing a crack

When the applied load increases, the crack should propagate forward. Along the crack path, the inclusions, such as fiber, play the role of arresting point for the crack propagation. Since the inclusion usually has a stochastic strength value, and is distributed randomly in space, the following assumption are introduced in this model.

1. The occurrence probability of a crack arresting-point in region $(x, x + \Delta x)$ is given by $\lambda(x)\Delta x$;
2. The probability for no crack arresting-point in region $(x, x + \Delta x)$ is given as $1 - \lambda(x)\Delta x$;
3. The occurrence probability for two and more crack arresting-points in this region is the higher-order smaller quantity as $o(\Delta x)$.

If the strength distribution of the crack arresting-point is given by F , $\lambda(x)\Delta x$ can be derived as following

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda(x)\Delta x &= \text{Prob}[\text{there is an inclusion in the region } (x, x + \Delta x)] \\ &\quad \bullet \text{ Prob}[\text{the inclusion will not break at the tip of the} \\ &\quad \text{crack under the action of external load}] \\ &= n\Delta x[1 - F] \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where n is the average number of the inclusions in unit length. In deriving Eqn (1), We assumed that distribution of the inclusions in space is statistically uniform.

If $P_0(x)$ is denoted as the probability that there is no crack arresting-point in region (x_0, x) , one can obtain

$$P_0(x + \Delta x) = P_0(x)[1 - \lambda(x)\Delta x] = P_0(x) - \lambda(x)P_0(x)\Delta x \tag{2}$$

Therefore, one can derive

$$\frac{dP_0(x)}{dx} = -\lambda(x)P_0(x) \quad (3)$$

The solution of equation (3) is given by

$$P_0(x) = \exp\left\{-\int_{x_0}^x \lambda(x)dx\right\} \quad (4)$$

If the crack starts to propagate from x_0 under the action of the external load, the probability for it to be arrested in the region $(z, z + \Delta z)$ is given by

$$\langle z|x_0 \rangle > \Delta z = \exp\left\{-\int_{x_0}^z \lambda(x)dx\right\} \lambda(z)\Delta z \quad (5)$$

therefore the probability density function of arresting the crack at z is given by

$$\langle z|x_0 \rangle = \lambda(z) \exp\left\{-\int_{x_0}^z \lambda(x)dx\right\} \quad (6)$$

Once the crack starts to propagate at x_0 , the probability for it to be arrested without increasing the load is given by

$$P_s = \int_{x_0}^{\infty} \langle z|x_0 \rangle dz = 1 - \exp\left\{-\int_{x_0}^{\infty} \lambda(z)dz\right\} \quad (7)$$

Therefore, once the crack starts to propagate at x_0 , the probability that it will propagate to infinity and induces the material to fracture is given by

$$P_f = 1 - P_s = \exp\left\{-\int_{x_0}^{\infty} \lambda(z)dz\right\} \quad (8)$$

As defined in Kunin[6], a load-specimen configuration is stable if $P_f = 0$, i.e., the crack will be arrested with probability 1, otherwise it is unstable.

The mean crack arrest length for cracks initiated at x_0 is

$$m_1(x_0) = \int_{x_0}^{\infty} \langle z|x_0 \rangle dz = x_0 + \int_{x_0}^{\infty} \exp\left\{-\int_{x_0}^z \lambda(x)dx\right\} dz \quad (9)$$

The above analysis is suitable for crack propagation spontaneously in a single excursion without increasing the load. In what following, we try to incorporate the effect of increasing load to derive the differential equation for determining the crack length distribution $p(x, \sigma)$.

Let us consider a loaded solid described in Fig.1. Denote by $\xi(\sigma)$ the random position of the crack tip at an external load σ , and by $P(x, \sigma)\Delta x$ the probability of finding the crack tip at a length x at the external load σ , assuming that at $\sigma = 0$ the tip was at x_0

$$p(x, \sigma)\Delta x = \text{Pr ob}[x \leq \xi(\sigma) \leq x + \Delta x | \xi(0) = x_0] \quad (10)$$

To relate $p(x, \sigma + \Delta\sigma)$ to the distribution $p(\bullet, \sigma)$ of crack locations at σ , notice first that the crack tip ends up at the length x at the load $\sigma + \Delta\sigma$ in one of the following mutually exclusion ways: during $\Delta\sigma$, it either propagated to x from one of the length z between the notch tip and x , $x_0 \leq z < x$, or it was at x at the load σ and remained there. By the formula of total probability, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} p(x, \sigma + \Delta\sigma)\Delta x &= \int_{x_0}^x \langle x|z \rangle dx \cdot \frac{dF}{d\sigma} \cdot P(z, \sigma)\Delta z\Delta\sigma \\ &+ (1 - \frac{dF}{d\sigma} \cdot \Delta\sigma) p(x, \sigma)\Delta x \\ &= \int_{x_0}^x \langle x|z \rangle p(z, \sigma) f(z, \sigma) dz \Delta x \Delta\sigma \\ &+ [1 - f(x, \sigma)\Delta\sigma] p(x, \sigma)\Delta x \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $f(z, \sigma) (= \frac{dF}{d\sigma})$ is the probability density function of strength for a crack arresting-point.

Rearranging equation (11), one can derive

$$\frac{\partial p(x, \sigma)}{\partial \sigma} = \int_{x_0}^x \langle x|z \rangle p(z, \sigma) f(z, \sigma) dz - f(x, \sigma) p(x, \sigma) \quad (12)$$

From equation (6), one obtains

$$\langle x|z \rangle = \lambda(z) \cdot \frac{\langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\langle z|x_0 \rangle} \quad (13)$$

Substitution of equation (13) into equation (12) yields

$$\frac{\partial p(x, \sigma)}{\partial \sigma} = \langle x|x_0 \rangle \int_{x_0}^x \lambda(z) p(z, \sigma) f(z, \sigma) / \langle z|x_0 \rangle dz - f(x, \sigma) p(x, \sigma) \quad (14)$$

Divide equation (14) by $\langle x|x_0 \rangle$ and denote

$$q(x, \sigma) = \frac{p(x, \sigma)}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle} \quad (15)$$

Then equation (14) becomes

$$\frac{\partial q(x, \sigma)}{\partial \sigma} = \int_{x_0}^x \lambda(x) f(z, \sigma) q(z, \sigma) dz - f(x, \sigma) q(x, \sigma) \quad (16)$$

Differentiating equation (16) in x , one obtains the following equation for q :

$$\frac{\partial^2 q(x, \sigma)}{\partial x \partial \sigma} = \lambda(x) f(x, \sigma) q(x, \sigma) - \frac{\partial f(x, \sigma)}{\partial x} q(x, \sigma) - f(x, \sigma) \frac{\partial q(x, \sigma)}{\partial x} \quad (17)$$

Substitution of equation (15) into equation (17) yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x \partial \sigma} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \left[f(x, \sigma) - \frac{1}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle} \frac{\partial \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial \sigma} \right] - \frac{\partial p}{\partial \sigma} \cdot \frac{1}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle} \cdot \frac{\partial \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial x} \\ & + p(x, \sigma) \left[\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - \lambda(x) f(x, \sigma) - \frac{1}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle} f(x, \sigma) \frac{\partial \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial x} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{2}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle^2} \cdot \frac{\partial \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial \sigma} - \frac{1}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial x \partial \sigma} \right] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Equation (18) can be expressed in the form as

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x \partial \sigma} + a(x, \sigma) \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + b(x, \sigma) \frac{\partial p}{\partial \sigma} + c(x, \sigma) p = 0 \quad (18')$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a(x, \sigma) &= f(x, \sigma) - \frac{1}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle} \cdot \frac{\partial \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial \sigma} \\ b(x, \sigma) &= -\frac{1}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle} \cdot \frac{\partial \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial x} \\ c(x, \sigma) &= \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - \lambda(x) f(x, \sigma) - \frac{1}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle} f(x, \sigma) \cdot \frac{\partial \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial x} \\ &+ \frac{2}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle^2} \cdot \frac{\partial \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial \sigma} \cdot \frac{\partial \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{\langle x|x_0 \rangle} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \langle x|x_0 \rangle}{\partial x \partial \sigma} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

From equation (6), one finds that if we know the microstructural characteristics of the material, represented by the average number of inclusions in unit length n , the strength distribution $F(\sigma)$ of the crack arresting-points and the applied load, the parameters $a(x, \sigma), b(x, \sigma), c(x, \sigma)$ can be determined easily. If the initial crack tip is at x_0 when $\sigma = 0$, the probability density function $p(x, \sigma)$ of the crack tip location at σ can be determined by equation (18') and the initial condition

$$\begin{aligned} p(x, \sigma) &= \delta(x - x_0) \\ p(x, \sigma) &= 0, x < x_0, \sigma \geq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

The derivation of equation (18) is quite similar with the work of Kunin[6], whereas in Kunin's work, the mode of crack growth was modeled by a Markovian stochastic pattern of a microscopic random jump, followed by a random waiting time, a random jump, and so on. In our model, the applied load plays the role of the time t . In the following part, as an example, the unidirectional fiber reinforced composite was considered in detail.

CRACK GROWTH IN UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBER COMPOSITES

In most composites of current interest, the extensional stiffness of the fibers is much greater than that of the matrix. As a result, the fibers support most of the load in case of uniaxial tensile loading. Considering a 90° -slit notch in a unidirectional composite (Fig.2), for it to extend in an unstable manner at an applied load, it is necessary that the intact fiber at the root of the notch breaks. This requires that the stress in this fiber exceeds its strength. Generally speaking, the fiber strength can be reasonably assumed to follow the Weibull distribution, therefore

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left\{ - \left(\frac{k_x \sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^\beta \right\} \tag{21}$$

where k_x is the stress concentration factor for the intact fiber at the tip x of the notch.

Fig.2: A 90° -Slit notch in unidirectional composite

To calculate the stress concentration factor for the intact fiber, following Zweben[1], the modified shear-lag model was used as shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3: Model for the analysis of stress concentrations including nonelastic matrix effect

It consists of a central core of n broken fibers separated from two adjacent intact fibers by a matrix region whose effective width is d . The intact fibers are representative of regions of fibers which are subjected to a stress concentration resulting from the notch. The intact fibers, in turn, are flanked by regions of matrix of width d , beyond which lies material which is assumed to have the behavior of overall composites, so as the part of central core.

Because of the large elastic shear stress concentration in the matrix at the root of the notch and the relatively weak interfacial strength and strength of most composite materials, it can be anticipated that there will be nonelastic effects such as debonding and plasticity in the matrix between the core and intact fibers at the root of the notch. We therefore include in the model a region of matrix in which the behavior is nonelastic, such as the interfacial slip. The axial dimension of this region is $2a$. In this nonelastic region, the shear stress is assumed to be constant and equal to the interfacial failure stress.

The boundary conditions at $x=0$ are zero stress in the core and zero displacement in the intact fibers. Because of the mixed boundary conditions, we choose as unknowns the axial displacements of the core and intact fibers, U_0 and U_1 , respectively. By using the nondimensional quantities, the equation of equilibrium are

$$\begin{aligned} n \frac{d^2 u_0}{d\xi^2} - 2\bar{\tau}_m &= 0 & 0 \leq \xi \leq \alpha & \quad (22) \\ \frac{d^2 u_1}{d\xi^2} - u_1 + \frac{E_f}{E_c} \xi + \bar{\tau}_m &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} n \frac{d^2 u_0}{d\xi^2} - 2(u_1 - u_0) &= 0 & \xi \geq \alpha & \quad (23) \\ \frac{d^2 u_1}{d\xi^2} + 2u_1 - u_0 - \frac{E_f}{E_c} \xi &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$u_i = \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{A_f d}{E_f G_m h} \right)^{-1/2} U_i, \quad \bar{\tau}_m = \left(\frac{G_m A_f}{E_f d h} \right)^{-1/2} \frac{1}{\sigma} \tau_m$$

$$\xi = \left(\frac{E_f A_f d}{G_m h} \right)^{-1/2} x, \quad \alpha = \left(\frac{E_f A_f d}{G_m h} \right)^{-1/2} a \quad (24)$$

and

- A_f = fiber cross-sectional area
- E_f = fiber extensional modulus
- E_c = composites extensional modulus
- G_m = matrix shear modulus
- α = nondimensional length
- d = fiber spacing
- h = material thickness
- u = nondimensional axial displacement
- ξ = nondimensional axial coordinate
- τ_m = matrix shear stress
- $\bar{\tau}_m$ = nondimensional shear stress
- σ = applied stress at infinity

The boundary conditions are

$$\frac{du_0(0)}{d\xi} = 0, \quad u_1(0) = 0,$$

$$\frac{du_0}{d\xi} = \frac{du_1}{d\xi} = 1 \quad \xi \rightarrow \infty \quad (25)$$

In addition, the displacements and forces should be continuous at $\xi = \alpha$, and also

$$u_1(\alpha) - u_0(\alpha) = -\bar{\tau}_m \quad (26)$$

By solving equations (22) and (23) under the given boundary condition, the stress concentration factor for the intact fiber at the tip of the notch which contains n broken fibers is given by

$$k_x(0) = \left. \frac{du_1(\xi)}{d\xi} \right|_{\xi=0} \quad (27)$$

The material constants are:

$$E_f = 360 \text{GN} / \text{m}^2, \nu_f = 0.4, \beta = 6.98, \sigma_0 = 355 \text{Mpa}, d = 8 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}, L = 25.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{m}$$

The results are shown in Fig.4

Fig. 4 The stress concentration factor for the intact fiber

Substituting the stress concentration factor into equation (21), then into equation(8), we obtain the failure probability of the specimen under the given applied load and the notch size. The results are shown in Fig.5 as the function of the interfacial strength τ_m between the fiber and matrix.

Fig.5 The failure probability of unidirectional composites with a notch

Fig.6. The average fracture stress of the notched specimen

To calculate the average fracture strength of the unidirectional composite with a notch, one can write,

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \int_0^{\sigma_{\max}} \sigma \frac{dp_f}{d\sigma} \cdot d\sigma = \sigma_{\max} - \int_0^{\sigma_{\max}} p_f d\sigma \quad (28)$$

where σ_{\max} is the utmost strength for all the specimens of the material, the result given by equation (28) is shown in Fig.6.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, a statistical model for crack growth in general heterogeneous solid was proposed based on the material microstructure and the strength distribution of the inclusion. As an example, the unidirectional fiber composite with a 90° -slit notch was considered in detail. We believe that the effect of the interfacial strength on the fracture stress was magnified due to the assumption that the fiber will break at the point with the maximum stress. In fact, the breaking point along the intact fiber should be widely dispersed due to the stochastic nature of the fiber strength.

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